

A Comparison of Museum Visitors' Expectations within the Context of Faith Tourism

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Abstract

Due to the functional diversification of museums in recent years, it has started to arouse interest in understanding the museum visitors' expectations and finding out whether their expectations are met or not. Therefore, this study aimed to identify and compare the expectations of domestic and foreign visitors of Mevlana Museum particularly within the context of faith tourism in Konya, Turkey. 163 domestic and 184 foreign visitors that visited the museum were surveyed with the questionnaire developed specifically for the research. Then, a factor analysis was conducted to reduce data and to clarify the dimensions, and finally five factors were obtained: attention and empathy, cultural impression, escapism, reminiscence and value for money. According to these findings, 80 % of the visitors seemed as having information about Mevlana while 57 % of the visitors were determined as having information about the Mevleviyeh. The findings of this study prove that the visitors of the museum mostly consist of informed ones. On the other hand, the expectation levels of the domestic visitors in attention and empathy and cultural impression dimensions were found higher while the expectations of both the domestic and the foreign visitors in terms of value for money dimension were similar.

Keywords: Domestic and foreign visitors, expectations, faith tourism, Mevlana Museum.

1. Introduction

Since the earliest times, there have been many factors that lead people to travel. Among these factors, especially the religious ones have been in the forefront since the middle age. Therefore, travelling for religious purposes started to become significant among all travels. One of the aims of religious journeys is one's desire to worship in these places. The other important aim is one's desire to visit sacred places and holy shrines no matter which religion he or she belongs to. In line with these aims, throughout history people have visited many different places of religious and scientific attractiveness. Among these attractions, museums hold an important place. In general, museums are defined as "places and buildings in which artistic and scientific works or useful objects for art and science are preserved and available

for public viewing” (TDK, 2005: 1445). However, Yılmaz (2011) draws attention to the fact that today the scope of the definition of “museum” has expanded in terms of tourism and has also covered places of religious interest.

The fact that the scope of museums has expanded and they becoming important tourist attractions have contributed to the importance of managing those areas as well as meeting the expectations of the visitors over time. Museum administrators are obliged to ensure visitors’ satisfaction particularly by capturing their imagination (Gartenhaus, 1997). Within this context, while taking measures not only to improve museums but also to increase the satisfaction level of visitors, it is of great importance to take into account of what expectations the visitors of museums have during these visits and in which direction of their perceptions have developed. Although museums have become complex and important tourist attractions today, it is observed that not many studies have been conducted on the expectations and satisfaction of the visitors. However, it is known that having little or no feedback from the visitors will fail to guide the museum administrators. Thus, the current study aims to find out and compare the expectations of both domestic and foreign tourists who visit Mevlâna Museum within the context of faith tourism. It is considered that the findings of the study will provide the museum administration with some leading insights and will guide further research to be conducted in this field in the near future.

2. Faith Tourism and Mevlâna Museum

Faith means “heartfelt attachment to a thought” (TDK, 2005). As a requirement of their faith, people are travelling for such spiritual purposes as "pilgrimage" and "seeing the holy places". It is known that not only pilgrims but even other people also visit those places out of curiosity and get involved in tour organizations for those places (Özgüç, 2003: 84). In this sense, Mecca and Medina in Islam, Jerusalem, Rome and Ephesus in Christianity, and again Jerusalem in Judaism are holy places of mass religious tourism. It is possible to increase the number of such holy places when taken into consideration of many parts of the world (Sargin, 2006: 3). In terms of tourism, those activities and events carried out to visit such places are described as “faith tourism”.

According to the definition made by the “Ministry of Culture and Tourism” of Turkey, faith tourism is identified as “the evaluation of touristic trips in the scope of tourism phenomenon, which are taken by people with the aims to fulfill their religious needs and see religious attractions outside the places in which they continually reside, work, and meet their usual needs” (Dikici and Sağır, 2012: 36). In Turkey, since the 1990s, activities to improve faith tourism have been attached importance by the Turkish Ministry of Culture and Tourism, and the inventory of the extant works of the three major religions and worship centers was created in 1993 (Kuter, 2008: 518). For this purpose, centers which are thought religiously important and visited mostly, are thought important in terms of the history of art, are the first of its kind and interesting due to the architectural features, are located in an easily accessible area and thus are included in tour programs by travel agencies have been evaluated in the scope of faith tourism. Many important structures and places, bearing the above-mentioned features, in Turkey have been opened to visitors within the scope of faith tourism, and it has been aimed to turn Turkey into an important centre of these tourist activities. Mevlâna Museum, situated in Konya, is one of these centers. Also known as a literary museum, Mevlevi Lodge and Mausoleum were first opened to visitors under the name of Konya Asar-ı Atika Museum in 1929 (Özkul *et al.*, 2012). In 1954, the museum was given the name of Mevlâna Museum. The current area of the museum (along with a rose garden) is 15,000 square meters. Mevlana Jalaluddin-i Rumi was the great Turkish thinker, Sufi, cleric and humanity poet who lived in Konya during the thirteenth century. This museum in which his

memory is kept alive is visited by foreign visitors who pay attention to his opinions as well as domestic visitors (Tapur, 2009: 484). Mevlâna Museum is the third-most-visited museum placed after Hagia Sophia and Topkapi in Turkey. In 2011, a total of 1, 735,424 people visited the museum (www.kulturvarliklari.gov.tr).

3. Museum Visitors' Expectations

Throughout the world, there has been a significant increase in the number of museums since the 19th century. Along with this period, the number of museum visits has increased and museums have become important places over this time. No doubt that this situation has played an important role in increasing interest in museums both in terms of tourism activities and management (Uralman, 2006: 252). In addition, along with the functional diversification of the museums (Weil, 2000), there has been an awakened interest over the issues of identifying what expectations the museum visitors have and finding out whether these expectations are met or not. Despite an increase in the number of studies on exploring this interest in recent years, it is interesting that there is a limited amount of academic research about this subject.

Museums, which play an important role because of being among tourist attractions, are generally known to focus on education, conservation and exhibition of works. However, it is also obvious that the visitors' expectations of trying such different experiences as entertainment and internal satisfaction have shown an increase (MacDonald and Alford, 1995; Moscardo, 1996; Kang and Gretzel, 2012).

Therefore, it has been crucial for museums to be able to understand and meet the expectations of visitor groups who wish to have different experiences from their visits to the museum (Moscardo, 1996; Kang and Gretzel, 2012). In this context, it is an important attempt to involve researchers from different academic units in the management of some museums with the purpose of understanding the expectations of people who visit the museums (Barnes and Lynch, 2012). Another point of view on the importance of the expectations of museum visitors has been suggested by Weil (2000). Weil (2000) stresses that being familiar with the expectations of museum visitors and meeting these expectations will help improve their quality of life. In the study carried out by Sheng and Chen (2012), it was also found out that there are a lot of factors influencing the experiences of museum visitors. Among these factors, the interaction of personal, social and environmental factors stand at the forefront.

In the literature relating tourism, there are only few studies based on the experiences of museum visitors. In this sense, a study conducted by Yılmaz (2011) on the Goreme Open Air Museum examined a total of 308 visitors' perceptions of service quality. In this study, their perceptions of quality were examined under four headings as "the physical elements of the service", "elements of exhibitions", "empathy" and "price, and other service elements". The results of the study show that the visitors expect higher quality service from all of these factors. In addition, it was found out that the visitors coming to the museum for the first time had low levels of quality perceptions. In another study carried out by Sheng and Chen (2012), the expectations of a total of 425 tourists who visited 5 different museums were evaluated (those museums were the Taiwan Museum, the Museum of Drinking Water, the National Museum of History, the National Taiwan Science Education Centre and the Miniatures Museum of Taiwan). At the end of the study, it was found out that the majority of visitors had the expectations of "comfort and entertainment".

4. Methodology

The main purpose of the study is to explore the expectations of tourists who visit Mevlâna Museum and compare the expectations of domestic and foreign visitors. With this purpose,

data were gathered from October 1 to December 1 (2012) through a questionnaire completed by 163 domestic and 184 foreign tourists who visited Mevlâna Museum. 37 out of the questionnaires filled out by the domestic visitors, and 16 out of those completed by the foreign visitors were not evaluated because they had the missing or incorrect information. The data base of this study consisted of 347 valid questionnaires.

The questionnaire used as a data collection tool was developed by taking into account of the studies by Barrio *et al.* (2009), İlhan (2009), Yılmaz (2011), Sheng and Chen (2012). The propositions drawn from these studies were associated with religious tourism. After the questionnaire form was constructed, a total of 68 domestic and foreign visitors were asked to respond the questionnaire form under the pilot study in order to check the reliability of the scale. Following this pre-application, the reliability of the questionnaire was found as 0.83. So, the questionnaire form consists of 23 items that prepared to find out the expectations of the visitors. In addition, 6 questions to determine the participants' experiences of their visit to the museum and 9 questions to identify their demographic characteristics are included to the form.

5. Findings of the Study

The findings regarding the characteristics of the participants are presented separately for domestic and foreign visitors as seen in Table 1. In this context, 55.3 % of the participants are domestic and 44.7% are foreign visitors. The majority of the participants are aged between 19 and 29, and 58.5% of them are single, and most of the participants are university graduates. Whereas 33.7% of the foreign participants have visited Mevlâna Museum with a tour group, 26.4% of the domestic participants have visited it along with their families. It has been identified that 16.7% of the foreign participants have come from European countries while 11.8% of them have come from the Far East countries.

Table 1: Profile of the respondents

	Domestic (N=163)		Foreign (N=184)		Total (N=347)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Gender						
Male	88	54	104	56.5	192	55.3
Female	74	46	80	43.5	155	44.7
Age						
19-29	93	57.1	97	52.7	190	54.8
20-39	33	20.2	26	14.2	59	17
40-49	26	16	23	12.5	49	14.1
50-59	8	4.9	19	10.3	27	7.8
60 and more	3	1.8	19	10.3	22	6.3
Marital Status						
Married	98	60.1	105	57.1	131	37.8
Single	60	36.8	71	38.6	204	58.5
Other	5	3.1	8	4.3	13	3.7
Education						
Primary School	12	7.4	2	1.1	14	4
High School	21	12.8	21	11.4	42	12.1
University	115	70.6	104	56.5	219	63.1
Master's	10	6.1	45	24.5	55	15.9
PhD	5	3.1	12	6.5	17	4.9
Travelling with whom						
Alone	29	17.8	37	20.1	66	19
Suppose	24	14.7	21	11.4	45	13
Family	43	26.4	42	22.8	85	24.5
Relatives	8	4.9	4	2.2	12	3.5
Travel Agency	29	17.8	62	33.7	91	26.2

Other	30	18.4	18	9.8	48	13.8
Nationality						
Turkey	163	100	-	-	163	47
Arabian Countries	-	-	21	6.1	21	6.1
Middle Asian Countries	-	-	19	5.4	19	5.4
Far Eastern Countries	-	-	41	11.8	41	11.8
European Countries	-	-	58	16.7	58	16.7
Russian Federation	-	-	2	0.6	2	0.6
South American Countries	-	-	28	8.1	28	8.1
North American Countries	-	-	1	0.3	1	0.3
African Countries	-	-	14	4	14	4

When the participants' experiences of their visit are examined, it has been observed that 64.8% of them have visited the museum before (Table 2). The majority of these participants have visited the museum one or two times. The rate of the participants who have knowledge about Mevlâna is 80.6% whereas the visitors who have knowledge about the Mevleviyeh rates 57% of the participants. Furthermore, it can be seen that 52.1% of the visitors have gathered information from different sources before they visited the museum, and 61.9% of them have particularly devoted time in their holiday schedule to visit the museum.

Table 2: Visiting experiences of the respondents (N=347)

Have you ever visited Mevlana Museum before?	n	%
Yes	225	64.8
No	122	35.2
If yes, how many times?	n	%
1	94	41.7
2	69	30.6
3	34	15.1
4	16	7.2
5 and more	12	5.4
I have information about Mevlana	n	%
Yes	280	80.6
No	67	19.4
I have information about the Mevleviyeh	n	%
Yes	198	57
No	149	43
I've collected information from different sources before visiting Mevlana Museum	n	%
Yes	181	52.1
No	166	47.9
I've spared some special time for today to visit Mevlana Museum in my holiday schedule	n	%
Yes	215	61.9
No	132	38.1

23 items produced which are to be able to identify how the visitors' expectations of the museum are grouped for testing the validity of the questionnaire and were analyzed through the exploratory factor analysis. The items with factor loading < 0.40 were excluded from evaluation. Until it reached a meaningful factor construct, the analysis was repeated in three stages. In the fourth stage, the 17 items, as referred to in Table 3, were grouped under five factors. In the analysis, those factors that have an eigenvalue >1 were evaluated. As a result of the factor analysis, the KMO value of the sampling was calculated as 0.846. The result of the Bartlett test (Sig.0.000) showed that a significant factor model can be established.

Table 3: Factor analysis and reliability test results of expectation. (N= 347)

Factors and Items	Factor Loading	Eigenvalue	Explained Variance (%)	Cronbach's Alfa
Factor 1 – Attention and Empathy		5,360	% 31,527	0.81
Mevlana Museum is a worldwide known faith tourism center.	,494			
While visiting Mevlana Museum, I would like to see other visitors' interest for the museum.	,664			
I expect not be disturbed by other visitors while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,697			
Just as expected from the visitors, I also expect the museum officials to behave in a good manner to keep silence and peace in the museum during the tours to Mevlana Museum.	,696			
I'd like to feel myself as one of the conscious visitors while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,506			
Factor 2 – Cultural Impression		1,688	% 9,931	0.79
While visiting Mevlana Museum, I expect the historical artifacts presented in the museum to evoke admiration on me artistically.	,607			
I expect the historical artifacts that I see in Mevlana Museum to influence me spiritually.	,730			
While visiting Mevlana Museum, I'd like to find out some interesting differences and changes between that age and today.	,468			
I'd like to relax and feel at peace while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,531			
Factor 3 – Escapism		1,422	% 8,362	0.77
I feel myself as a part of history while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,462			
While visiting Mevlana Museum, I feel as if I lived in the same age with the historical artifacts presented in the museum.	,933			
I visualize the legendary characters or events of that age while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,476			
Factor 4 – Reminiscence		1,117	%6,568	0,74
I'd like to buy souvenirs while visiting Mevlana Museum.	,414			
I'd like to have good memories that will remind me the Museum after the visit.	,881			
I'd like to feel that I've gained a new aspect of future after visiting Mevlana Museum.	,504			
Factor 5 – Value for Money		1,036	%6,096	0,72
I'd like to feel that the payment of museum entrance is worth for the visit.	,765			
After visiting Mevlana Museum, I'd like to feel that the payment I've made is worth for the souvenirs.	,702			

1- strongly disagree 5- strongly agree

As the result of factor analysis, five factors were identified as “attention and empathy”, “cultural impression”, “escapism”, “reminiscence” and “value for money”. The total variance of these five factors is 62.4% that means they can be explained. Among these, the variance explanation rate of the "attention and empathy" factor is 31.5%.

Table 4: T-test results between domestic and foreign visitors

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		T-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-uçlu)
Attention and Empathy	Assumed*	1,453	,229	8,063	345	,000
	Not assumed**			8,114	344,908	,000
Cultural Impression	Assumed*	,289	,591	7,115	245	,000
	Not assumed**			7,135	343,119	,000
Escapism	Assumed*	1,500	,222	4,581	345	,000
	Not assumed**			4,568	335,612	,000
Reminiscence	Assumed*	0,339	,561	2,181	345	,031
	Not assumed**			2,174	334,415	,030
Value for Money	Assumed*	3,279	,071	1,743	345	,082
	Not assumed**			1,725	314,771	,086

* Equal variances assumed ** Equal variances not assumed

An independent t-test was employed in order to compare the expectations of domestic and foreign tourists who visited Mevlâna Museum. The result of analysis points out that the domestic and foreign visitors do not show any differences only in their expectations of the "value for money" factor (Table 4).

Table 5: Post-Hoc comparisons after T-test

		N	Cumulative Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Attention and Empathy	Domestic Visitors	163	21,5583	3,10137	,24292
	Foreign Visitors	184	18,7065	3,44524	,25399
Cultural Impression	Domestic Visitors	163	17,4049	2,64724	,20735
	Foreign Visitors	184	15,3261	2,77620	,20466
Escapism	Domestic Visitors	163	11,3804	2,54153	,19907
	Foreign Visitors	184	10,1576	2,42756	,17896
Reminiscence	Domestic Visitors	163	11,4601	2,47268	,19368
	Foreign Visitors	184	10,8967	2,33650	,17225
Value for Money	Domestic Visitors	163	7,4724	2,21196	,17325
	Foreign Visitors	182	7,0934	1,82283	,13512

The responses of the domestic and foreign visitors were compared to determine the sources of these differences in their expectations. As can be seen in Table 5, the expectation levels of the domestic visitors are higher than those of the foreign visitors. Especially the difference in terms of the first two factors is at a higher level.

6. Results and Discussion

In this study, the expectations of domestic and foreign visitors who visited Mevlâna Museum were measured and compared. For this purpose, the data were collected through a questionnaire form conducted with a total of 163 domestic and 184 foreign visitors who visited the Mevlâna Museum. In order to evaluate the expectations for the museum in the study, the questionnaire was developed by benefitting from the studies by Barrio *et al.*, (2009), İlhan (2009), Yılmaz (2011), and Sheng and Chen (2012). Following this, a factor analysis was conducted to determine how the items included in the questionnaire were grouped. As a result of the factor analysis, the five factors referred as "attention and

empathy", "cultural impression", "escapism", "reminiscence" and "value for money", and 17 items were identified. The total variance of these five factors is 62.4%. The study presents some crucial findings as to the experiences of the visitors. For example, it is pointed out that 80% of the visitors have knowledge about Mevlâna while 57% of them have information about the Mevleviyeh. Moreover, 52 % of the visitors obtained information from different sources before their visit to Mevlâna Museum. It can also be considered that these findings show that the participants of this study visited the museum consciously.

The tourists' expectations of their visit to Mevlâna Museum vary with respect to such dimensions as "attention and empathy", "cultural impression", "escapism" and "reminiscence" in terms of domestic and foreign visitors. The domestic visitors' expectations as to these four factors are at a higher level than those of the foreign visitors. In particular, the perception levels of domestic visitors in terms of "attention and empathy" and "cultural impression" are much higher. This point can be occurred due to the domestic visitors' beliefs. Moreover, such a difference can be explained by that the domestic visitors are generally motivated and conscious in their visits to Mevlâna Museum. Another interesting finding of the study is that the expectations for the factor referred as "value for money" do not show any difference in terms of domestic and foreign visitors. The cumulative arithmetic average for this factor is low, so this can be considered as an indicator of the fact that financial expectations are slightly significant during their visits to Mevlâna Museum (Table 5). This finding is valid for both domestic and foreign visitors of the museum.

According to those findings, some suggestions should be made as listed here. Firstly, it is suggested that the expectations in the context of "attention and empathy" and "cultural impression" should be taken into consideration in museum planning. Hence, it should also be suggested museum managers may train the staff with regard to "attention and empathy" dimension. Because of being important from the point of the visitors, museum managers need to ensure the continuity of cultural impression dimension which includes the artifacts and the atmosphere itself. Finally, the academicians who are enthusiastic in this subject should make a detailed research focusing on "attention and empathy" and "cultural impression" dimensions and their variables.

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